

THE WILLINGNESS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO CHOICE OF
AQUACULTURE AS A CAREER IN OKITIPUPA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE,
NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the willingness of secondary school students to choice of aquaculture as a profession in Okitipupa Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample was made up of 100 science students randomly selected among science students in two public secondary schools. Questionnaire was used in data collection. Data were analysed by the use of frequency counts, percentages and Chi-square. The findings revealed among others that 52% of respondents were aware of Aquaculture as a profession, 56% were willing to study aquaculture with the award of scholarship; gender and parental educational level are not significant to the willingness of secondary school students to study aquaculture ($p>0.05$). It follows that interest of students in the profession should be aroused starting from the secondary school levels. Based on this study, it is recommended that Governments, public and private organizations, individuals and NGOs should embark on various enlightenment programmes and motivation of students at secondary schools to encourage the study of aquaculture as a profession.

KEYWORDS: Aquaculture, career, secondary school, student

INTRODUCTION

In view of the importance of aquaculture in global fish supplies and particularly in Nigeria, there appears therefore, an urgent need to arouse the interest of students in aquaculture so as to increase the intensification of fish production through various modern methods. Increasingly, young Nigerians have been choosing careers in Animal science, Soil science, Crop science and other areas of Agriculture. Less frequently they have chosen careers in Aquaculture. Such choices may reflect the current economy (Maureen, 1983). In most cases, students are easily prepared to imbibe new ideas and principles of existence. Once students get used to particular ideology, and then often stick to it (Ajayi and Gbile, 1995). Before students could be used to propagate any new concept of idea, they need to be convinced, educated and enlightened. If students are informed, they can be counted as agents of change (Faleyimu, *et al* 2009).

Despite the prospect and importance of aquaculture in any nation's socio-economic development, years of neglect of this course by students have left very huge gaps in producing enough experts in aquaculture. One of the tasks of high school students is to explore and plan for their postsecondary career options. Developmental theory of career development, states that high school students are at the exploration stage of career development, which involves crystallizing and specifying their occupational preferences, while also making preliminary decisions about their career choice Super's (1990). To assist students' career development, the national standards of the American School Counselor Association (ASCA, 1997) thus require that students have competence in career decision-making.

There is support for the idea that enough stability of personality, ability, and value exists from early adolescence through middle adolescence to predict satisfaction in later adolescence college or undergraduate placement. Not only preparation in academic areas but also participation in activities influences career choice (Mauree, 1983). The content standards for career development guide the school counseling program to provide the foundation for the acquisition of skills, attitudes, and knowledge that enable students to make a successful transition from school to the world of work, and from job to job across the life career span. Career development includes the employment of strategies to achieve future career success and job satisfaction as well as fostering understanding of the relationship between personal qualities, education and training, and the world of work (ASCA, 1997). Capable students are likely to be perceptive about their own interests and aptitudes at an early age and thus are

often able to choose careers that are realistic and appropriate to their personal qualities. The intellectually less capable on the other hand, tend to make relatively unrealistic career plans that they must change later. This paper however, examines the willingness of secondary school students to choice of aquaculture as a career in Okitipupa local government area of Ondo state, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Okitipupa, Okitipupa Local Government Area of Ondo State, which is located in rain forest zone of Nigeria. Two public secondary schools were randomly selected from the local government; one hundred students were randomly selected and questionnaire was used in collecting data for this. The questionnaire that was used in collecting data for this study was a two-section close ended. The first section was designed to collect data on demographic characteristics and the second section has items solely on the indicators of the variables under investigation. The question was clearly defined with the described responses as either 'Yes' or 'No'. Respondents were asked to tick appropriately, which reflected his or her choice. The statistical methods that were used in analyzing the data include frequency counts, percentages and Chi-square.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals that there is almost equal (gender) of students selected for the survey. In a similar study, (Faleyimu, *et al* 2009) reported almost equal number of gender among students. Hence, any programme that takes cognizance of the youths will surely exhibit continuity, wide coverage and general acceptability (Ajayi and Gbile, 1995).

Table1: Gender distribution of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	51	51
Female	49	49
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 2: shows that 63% of respondents' parents have Higher National Diploma and above, this is followed by National Certificate of Education holders (25%) only a parent has no formal education (1%).

Table 2: Parental educational level (father)

Educational level	Frequency	Percentages
HND/B.Sc/M.Sc/PhD	63	63
NCE/ND	25	25
Secondary School Certificate	9	9
Primary School Certificate	2	2
No formal Education	1	1
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 3 indicates that 62% of the respondents were civil servants, 30% works in private establishments. While 8% are engaged in agriculture.

Table 3: Parental Occupational level (father)

Occupational level	Frequency	Percentages
Civil Servant	62	62
Private Establishment	30	30
Fish farmer	4	4
Arable/Cash crop farmer	4	4
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 4 indicates that 52% of respondents were aware of Aquaculture. Television was the highest source of information on Aquaculture (71%) followed by radio (13%) and least was through Teachers at school (3%).

Table 4: Information on Aquaculture as a profession and source of information

	Frequency	Percentages
Information of Aquaculture		
Yes	52	52
No	48	48
Total	100	100
Source of Information		
Radio	13	13
Television	71	71
Newspaper	6	6
Family members	7	7
Teachers	3	3
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 5 reveals that without any reinforcement such as the award of scholarship, only 9% of the respondents were willing to study Aquaculture in the higher institution. However, most of the students would like to study medicine; this is followed by those who preferred to study Engineering. In a similar study, (Faleyimu, *et al* 2009) reported higher percentage of students willing to study medicine compared to other courses.

Table 5: Courses preferred by respondents without reinforcement (award of scholarship)

Course preferred	Frequency	Percentages
Aquaculture	9	9
Medicine	60	60
Engineering	24	24
Education	2	2
Computer science	3	3
Arts	2	2
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 6 shows that 56% of the respondents were willing to study aquaculture in the higher Institution if they were given scholarship while 44% strongly detest aquaculture, that even if they were offered scholarship, they would not study it. Not only academic areas but also participation in activities influences career choice (Maureen 1983). Baid (1982) reported that there is correlation between personal characteristics and activities with career choice.

Table 6:Willingness to study Aquaculture in the higher institution with reinforcement (scholarship).

Study Aquaculture with scholarship	Frequency	Percentages
Yes	56	56
No	44	44
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 7: shows that 58% of students were neutral about their future perception of aquaculture while 42% believed the future is bright. Forty-three percent of the respondent attributed reason why aquaculture is not as competitive as other courses to lack of awareness, 30% stated opportunity ahead while 27% listed job after study.

Table 7: Respondents perception of Aquaculture as a profession in Nigeria and reasons why Aquaculture is not competitive

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Perception of Aquaculture:		
Future is bright	42	42
I can't say	58	58
Total	100	100
Reasons why Aquaculture is not competitive		
No awareness	43	43
Opportunity ahead	30	30
Job after study	27	27
Total	100	100

Source: field work 2011

Table 8: reveals that 33% of the respondents agreed that government can promote aquaculture if it could be included in the school curriculum. This is followed by students who agreed that creating awareness on Television and radio could be made 30%. Only 11% were of the opinion that government should provide incentives to graduates of aquaculture.

Table 8: Government action to promote aquaculture as a profession

Government action	Frequency	Percentages
Aquaculture subjects in school curriculum	33	33
Creating awareness on television and radio	30	30
Job available for aquaculture graduate	26	26
Incentives for aquaculture graduate	11	11
Total	100	100

Source: fieldwork, 2011

The Chi-square in table 9 reveals that gender has no significant influence ($p>0.05$) on the study of aquaculture. This showed that the choice or hatred for aquaculture is not related to sex.

Table 9: Chi-square test of gender and willingness to study Aquaculture

	Value	DFA	Asymp	Sig
Pearson chi-square	0.967	1	0.325	NS
Likelihood ratio	0.968	1	0.325	NS
Linear-by-linear association	0.957	1	0.328	NS
No of valid class	100			

Not significant at 0.05

Chi-square in table 10: shows that parent's educational level and source of income or employers has no significant relationship ($p>0.05$) with the choice of courses of study in higher institution. This showed that parent's educational level and where they work does not determine the career choice of their words.

Table10: Chi-square test of parental educational level and willingness to offer aquaculture.

	Value	DFA	Asymp	Sig
Pearson chi-square	7.705	4		NS
Likelihood ratio	8.987	4		NS
Linear-by-linear association	1.700	1		NS
No of valid class	100			

Not significant at 0.05

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Students preferred to study aquaculture as a profession if there is incentive in form of scholarship, gender and parental educational level has no significant relationship with the choice of aquaculture in higher institution. It is recommended that Governments, public and private organizations, individuals and NGOs should embark on various enlightenment programmes and motivation of students at secondary schools to encourage the study of aquaculture as a profession.

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